

FAR EASTERN UNIVERSITY
Institute of Accounts, Business and Finance
Student Apprenticeship Program

SEC 13

A Report on Student Apprenticeship Program – 2nd Semester - AY 2022 - 2023

Presented to
Institute of Accounts, Business and Finance
Far Eastern University – Manila

Submitted by:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Leonardo F. Cada, Jr.'.

Leonardo F. Cada, Jr.
SAP Adviser

Submitted to:

Paul Martin Hernandez, MBA
SAP Coordinator

Endorsed by:

Joselito P. Tem, Ed.D
Associate Dean, FEU-IABF

Noted by:

Enrique Lozari, Ph. D.
Dean, FEU-IABF

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A. INTRODUCTION

On-the-job (OJT) training is a course requirement for students to immerse themselves in a work environment by applying the theories, principles and ideas learned in the academe (Department of Labor and Employment On the-Job Training Manual, 2015 as cited by Cada, Jr.,2020). OJT students under Section 17, who were enrolled in the 2nd semester, SY 2022 - 2023 have successfully complied well with all the course requirements. These students have performed their various tasks and responsibilities under the program in various host companies within Metro Manila, Philippines for a period of one (1) semester equivalent to 550 hours.

B. APPRENTICE DATA

A total of 39 students enrolled in various Business Administration programs have completely rendered their respective internship hours in various host companies in Metro Manila.

Table 1
Profile of the Students

	Frequency	Percentage
As to Gender		
Male	20	51%
Female	19	49%
Total	39	100%
As to Program		
Accountancy	0	0%
Business Administration	39	100%
Internal Audit	0	0%
Total	39	100%
As to Marital Status		
Single	39	100%
Married	0	0%
Total	39	100%
As to whether graduating or non-graduating		
Graduating	39	100%
Non-graduating	0	0%
Total	39	100%

C. COMPANY PROFILE

1. Nature of Company or Business

The OJT students for this 2nd semester, AY 2022 – 2023 were well distributed to the different host companies. The highest number of OJT students in one host company was six (6) and that of the Bureau of Internal Revenue, a public institution.

Table 2
Company

Company	Frequency	Percentage
American Insurance Association (AIA)	4	10
Ayala Property Management Corp.	1	2.5
BUREAU OF INTERNAL REVENUE - INTRAMUROS	6	16
Cerebrum Design Studio	1	2.5
Citi Global Realty and Development Inc.	3	8
Commission on Audit	1	2.5
Cocogen Insurance (Manila)	1	2.5
Essilor Shared Service Philippines, Inc.	1	2.5
COCOGEN INSURANCE INC.	1	2.5
Direct Business Technologies, Inc.	1	2.5
First Place, Inc. (FPI)	2	5
Global Tiger Solutions	1	2.5
Government Service Insurance System (GSIS)	1	2.5
ITC CORP.	1	2.5
MIMS PH	1	2.5
Philippine Merchant Marine School Manila (PMMS)	2	5
PROACCT OF REYES KING ASSOCIATES	1	2.5
PruLife UK	2	5
PwC AC Manila	1	2.5
Reed Elsevier	1	2.5
Rhand Rhelle Sneakers Supply (Gateway Mall Cubao Branch)	1	2.5
Sun Life Financial - BAOBAB NBO (Kashmir Sapphire Unit)	1	2.5
Velray Real Estate Services OPC	1	2.5
XIRRUS INC	2	5
TOTAL	39	100%

Description

2. Company Size

As per student consultations, they narrated that they were able to do their tasks effectively because their supervisors have provided them with good training directions.

Table 3
Size of the Company/Business in Terms of Employees

Number of Employees	Frequency	Percentage
1 - 9 employees	3	13%
10 - 99 employees	4	17%
100 - 199 employees	8	32%
200 employees and above	9	38%
Total	24	100%

Description

3. Number of Employees

The number of employees as provided in Table 3 is based on SMED Council Resolution No. (2003) and Republic Act No.9501 (2008).

4. Location

Table 4
Location of the Companies/Businesses

Location of the Companies/Businesses	Frequency	Percentage
Manila City	6	25%
Quezon City	8	20%
Makati	5	40%
Taguig	3	8%
Pasay	2	
Total	24	100%

Host companies or Host Training Establishments (HTEs) are business enterprises offering OJT or apprenticeship opportunities. These HTEs, must partner with a Higher Education Institution (HEI) and must have government recognition if it is a private school, an appropriate board resolution if it is a State University or College, or a local government ordinance if a local university or college. If the school does not have any of these, it cannot offer a practicum subject (Cada, Jr., 2020 citing CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 23, Series of 2009). These host companies or HTEs were from the private and public sectors.

Description

D. APPRENTICE PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

1. Job Positions and Department Assignment

Start here.

Table 5
Average Grade for each Group Criteria in the Evaluation Form

Description	Average
Work Output and Quality of Work	9.23
Communication Skills	9.28
Job Knowledge and Organization	9.26
Judgment and Initiative	9.20
Personality	9.20
Cooperation	9.33
Diligence and Reliability	9.41
Ability to Learn	9.53
Attendance and Punctuality	9.43
Personal Appearance	9.74
Total Average	100

1. Work Output and Quality of Work

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their work output and quality of work with average rating of 9.23 across gender, nature of work and host companies.

2. Communication Skills

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their communication skills with average rating of 9.28 across gender, nature of work and host companies.

3. Job Knowledge and Organization

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their job knowledge and organization with average rating of 9.26 across gender, nature of work and host companies.

4. Judgement and Initiative

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their judgement and initiative with average rating of 9.20 across gender, nature of work and host companies. But there are also a significant number of interns in which, this item became their weakness.

5. Personality

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their personalities as they have shown enthusiasm and eagerness to learn with average rating of 9.20 across gender, nature of work and host companies.

6. Cooperation

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their cooperation with average rating of 9.33 across gender, nature of work and host companies.

7. Diligence and Reliability

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their diligence and reliability with average rating of 9.41 across gender, nature of work and host companies.

8. Ability to Learn

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their ability to learn with average rating of 9.53 across gender, nature of work and host companies.

9. Attendance and Punctuality

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their attendance and punctuality with average rating of 9.43 across gender, nature of work and host companies.

10. Personal Appearance

Majority of the interns got positive feedbacks on their personal appearance with average rating of 9.74 across gender, nature of work and host companies.

E. EMPLOYABILITY OF THE APPRENTICE

Table 6
Summary of Trainees' Employability

Employability	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	39	100%
No	0	0
Total	39	100%

As per observations by the respective supervisor of all the interns in various host companies, finding of employability for all interns is positive.

Table 7
Summary of Trainees' Performance

Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Passed	39	100%
Failed	0	0
Withdrawn	0	0
Total	39	100%

Only the 39 interns under Section 13 have successfully passed the OJT program.

F. ACTUAL NUMBER OF STUDENTS WITH JOB OFFER BY THEIR HOST COMPANY

As per consultation with the students, 4 were offered a job in their host company.

G. ACTUAL NUMBER OF STUDENTS WHO ACCEPTED THE OFFER

2 accepted the offer and will start immediately, 2 were undecided and still looking for better opportunities.

H. SUMMARY OF APPRENTICE'S STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

Strengths:

- Most interns show enthusiasm and display willingness to get the job done
- Most interns are proactive.
- Most students communicate well.

Weaknesses:

- Punctuality
- Significant number of interns have judgement and initiative concerns. They tend to ask questions more often than taking initiatives. Maybe because the students are afraid to commit mistakes.

I. EXHIBITS OF SAP STUDENTS IN ACTION

J. SUGGESTION TO IMPROVE STUDENT APPRENTICESHIP PROGRAM (SAP)

1. From Apprentice

There were a significant number of students who were suggesting that the companies should given them tasks that must be useful to them, where they will learn, especially when they apply for work, not some random tasks.

2. From Industry Mentor or Supervisor

Allow the interns to undergo basic communication skills training before deployment to host companies.

3. SAP Adviser

Companies should utilize their interns as serious as possible, not just for their convenience in getting manpower, but to organize their policies on how to properly handle their interns. There are some interns that said they only had minimal learnings from their host companies.

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